

Interferences generated on the well-being of local communities by the activity of online platforms for tourist accommodation

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To cite this article: José Maria Martín-Martín , Juan F. Prados-Castillo , Juan de Dios Jiménez Aguilera & Eva Porras González (2020): Interferences generated on the well-being of local communities by the activity of online platforms for tourist accommodation, Journal of Sustainable Tourism, DOI: [10.1080/09669582.2020.1861455](https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1861455)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1861455>

Published online: 18 Dec 2020.

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